

SOCIAL CLASS AND EDUCATIONAL OPPORTUNITIES: A STUDY OF IKOT EKPENE LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA.

Anietie Jonah Udoh

Legislative Centre for Security Analysis (LeCeSa)
National Institute for Legislative and Democratic Studies (NILDS), Abuja
Email: anietie.udoh@nils.gov.ng.
Phone: +2348063028197

Eno Nnamdie Ekpo

Department of Sociology and Anthropology
Faculty of Social Sciences
University of Uyo
enonnamdie76@gmail.com
07065330494

Abstract

Children who live in low-income or informal housing may have limited access to educational resources, including schools, libraries, and technology. In addition, the neighbourhood may not be conducive for educational success, with limited safety and violence that affect learning. These disparities in educational opportunities may result in lower educational achievement and diminished future prospects for individuals, families and the society at large. This study examined the effect of social class and educational opportunities in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Anchored on class conflict theory, the study employed survey research design, primary and secondary source were used in collecting data from the population of 178697. The sample size used for this study was 342 gotten from Taro Yamani formula. The study adopted stratified sampling techniques. The instrument for data collection was a structure items of questionnaire, designed in line with the objective of the study. The data collected were analyzed using frequency tables, simple percentages, Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used in testing the hypotheses. Findings from the study revealed that; there is a significant influence of income status on educational opportunities in Ikot Ekpene Local Government; also, there is a significant occupation on educational opportunities in Ikot Ekpene Local Government; the finding also revealed that there is a significant influence of neighbourhood on educational opportunities in Ikot Ekpene Local Government. The study recommended among others that, local governments and educational institutions should develop and promote financial aid programmes, scholarships, and grants specifically targeting low-income families. This can help alleviate the financial burden on parents and students, enabling them to pursue education without the fear of insurmountable costs.

Keyword: Social Class, Educational Opportunities.

Introduction

The relationship between social class and educational opportunities has been a subject of interest and controversy in various societies. In Nigeria, like many other

developing countries, social class plays a significant role in determining access to quality education and academic success. According to Micklewright and Schnepf (2007), children from lower social classes in Nigeria are more likely to attend substandard schools with limited resources and inadequate facilities. They are also more likely to drop out of school due to financial constraints and lack of support structures at home. On the other hand, children from higher social classes have access to better schools, well-qualified teachers, and extracurricular activities that enhance their academic performance and future prospects.

Several studies including Brodowicz (2024) and Gimba (2018), have highlighted the impact of social class on educational opportunities in Nigeria. A study by Ogunmade (2015) found that children from high-income families are more likely to enrol in private schools, which are generally perceived to offer better quality education compared to public schools. Another study by Adekola and Dada (2018) revealed that children from lower social classes have limited access to educational resources such as textbooks, computers, and tutoring services, which are essential for academic success.

Also, according to Smith (2018), social class can have a profound impact on educational attainment, with individuals from lower socio-economic backgrounds facing greater challenges in accessing quality education and achieving academic success. Additionally, studies by Johnson, Stevens & Arthur (2019) have highlighted the role of parental education and income level in shaping educational opportunities for children, further underscoring the importance of social class in determining educational outcomes.

In Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area, a region known for its diverse social fabric and economic disparities, understanding the relationship between social class and educational opportunities is essential for addressing inequalities and promoting educational equity. Furthermore, a study by Udoh and Udom (2019) highlighted the impact of social class on educational outcomes in Ikot Ekpene, showing that students from higher social classes tend to perform better academically, have higher graduation rates, and are more likely to pursue higher education compared to their counterparts from lower social classes. The study also emphasised the role of socio-economic factors in shaping educational opportunities and success in the region. Moreover, Otu, Akpan, and Itoro (2020) conducted a study on the relationship between social class and educational attainment in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area, emphasising that disparities in social class contribute significantly to inequality in access to quality education. The research highlighted the need for targeted interventions and policies to address the educational disadvantages faced by individuals from lower social classes in the region.

The disparities in educational opportunities based on social class have far-reaching consequences for individuals and society as a whole. Limited educational opportunities for individuals from lower social classes can perpetuate the cycle of poverty and hinder social mobility. On the other hand, individuals from higher social classes have better chances of securing high-paying jobs and achieving economic success through the various educational opportunities at their disposal. Income status, occupation, and neighbourhood often limit the educational opportunities of individuals from lower socio-economic backgrounds. In light of these challenges, it is crucial to understand the factors that contribute to the unequal distribution of educational opportunities in Nigeria by conducting a comprehensive study on social class and educational opportunities in Ikot Ekpene local government Area of Nigeria, policymakers, educators, and stakeholders can develop strategies to address these disparities and ensure that all children have equal access to quality education, regardless of their social

background.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the abundant human and natural resources for development, Africa as a whole and Nigeria in particular is still confronted with poverty, which remains the preeminent contender for development attention (Udoh, 2025). The gap between the rich and the poor is very wide in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area, the rich become richer, the poor continue to be poorer, and this inequality has brought about school dropouts from homes that cannot afford even two square meals in a day. When these potential future leaders drop out from school, some of them will engage in frivolous acts, which brings instability to Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.

In Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area, there exists a disparity in educational opportunities based on social class, with individuals from lower socio-economic backgrounds facing greater challenges in accessing quality education compared to those from higher social classes. This inequality in educational opportunities perpetuates a cycle of disadvantage and limits social mobility for individuals from disadvantaged backgrounds. According to Duru, Edem, and Inyang (2017), social class is a key determinant of educational opportunities in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area. The study revealed that children from higher social classes have greater access to quality education, resources, and opportunities compared to those from lower social classes. This disparity in access to educational resources based on social class often perpetuates a cycle of inequality and limits the social mobility of individuals from disadvantaged backgrounds.

Since children from disadvantaged homes are not able to have access to education, they resort to criminal activities, such as armed robbery, kidnapping, prostitution, violence, cultism etc. According to Asuquo and Ekanem (2023), violence is a common decimal in every society or state. This occurs as certain group of perceived injustice, unfairness and inequality. This has certainly led to violence and crime in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area. As observed by Esara, Asuquo and Udoh (2024), there are prevalent cases of child theft in public places such as schools, churches, mosques, hospitals, markets and public events. It is now difficult to protect lives and properties. Esara, Asuquo, Ekanem, Samuel (2023) posited that subsequently, every existing state in the world today has an established government vested with the rights and responsibility to protect lives and property of her citizens. Lack of educational opportunities have dragged young people to making the place a danger zone.

The Educational Opportunities available to students in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area are often determined by their family's income and wealth status. Lower-income families often lack the financial resources to access quality educational opportunities, such as preschool and early childhood education, leading to lower rates of enrolment and higher dropout rates in primary and secondary school. This inequality in educational opportunity can have lasting consequences for an individual's future prospects, including lower rates of high school graduation and college enrolment, which may lead to a perpetuation of poverty and inequality across generations.

Furthermore, Educational Opportunities available to persons in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area are determined by their Neighbourhood status. Children who live in low-income or informal housing may have limited access to educational resources, including schools, libraries, and technology. In addition, the Neighbourhood may not be conducive for

Educational success, with limited safety and violence that affect learning. These disparities in Educational opportunities may result in lower educational achievement and diminished future prospects for individuals and families. Ekanem and Asuquo (2024) argued that, in career selection, students encounter a lot of issues/challenges; ranging from social, economic, cultural, financial etc.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to investigate the influence of social class on educational opportunities in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.

The specific objectives of the study are as follows:

- i. To access the Income status on Educational Opportunities in Ikot Ekpene Local Government.
- ii. To examine the effects of Occupation on Educational Opportunities in Ikot Ekpene Local Government.

Research Hypotheses

H₀1: There is no significant influence of income status on educational opportunities in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.

H₀2: There is no significant influence of Occupation on educational opportunities in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.

Review of Related Literature

Overview of Social Class and Income Status

The conceptualization of social class has evolved over time, with different theories and approaches being proposed by scholars. Marx's theory of social class emphasizes the relationship between the means of production, capital, and the allocation of resources (Marx, 1867). Weber, on the other hand, argued that social class is determined by multiple factors including occupation, wealth, and social status (Weber, 1922). Bourdieu's theory of social class includes both economic and cultural capital, emphasizing the importance of cultural practices and norms in shaping social class (Bourdieu, 1984).

One of the key areas where social class has a significant impact is on education. Numerous studies have found that children from higher social classes tend to have better educational outcomes compared to their lower-class counterparts (Breen and Goldthorpe, 1997; Reay et al., 2005). Factors such as access to high-quality schools, resources, and cultural capital are identified as key drivers of this disparity. Research has also pointed out the role of social class in influencing educational aspirations and opportunities for upward mobility (Erikson and Jonsson, 1996; Hällsten and Szulkin, 2019). As observed by Esara, Asuquo and Udoh (2024), the cause of militancy in Niger Delta Region of Nigeria is as a result of continuous deprivation and environmental degradation in the oil rich region without meaningful compensation from the oil proceed. As seen by Esara, Asuquo, Obonah and Eshiet (2024), the struggle for land and other natural resources is responsible for most communal conflicts in Akwa Ibom State. This can be traced to inequality and social class.

Asuquo and Ekanem (2023) posited that, when education is compromised, it becomes challenging to produce a workforce that can contribute meaningfully to various sectors, hindering economic growth and diversification. According to Ekanem, Asuquo, Ogar and Ofuka (2023), although women are discouraged from voting in some contexts (as

men and women in most democracies tend to vote at about the same rate), there is a change attributed to gender equality in education and even in career progression. Udoh (2024) argued that, gender inequality is a problem to human existence, health relationships and development. Obviously, gender inequality in Nigeria is not a new phenomenon (Udoh and Ekanem, 2024). It is a general problem to human existence, healthy relationships and development.

Several factors influence income status. Studies have identified education as a significant determinant of income, with higher education levels associated with higher incomes (Bishop and Mont, 2020; Oreopoulos and Petronijevic, 2020). Furthermore, research shows that occupation choice and job skills play a vital role in income attainment (Duncan and Murnane, 2014). Alongside education and occupation, gender has been highlighted as a key determinant of income status. Numerous studies have demonstrated that women tend to earn less than men, commonly referred to as the gender pay gap (Blau and Kahn, 2017; Killewald and Gough, 2020). Discrimination and societal norms contribute significantly to this disparity.

Income status has been shown to be strongly associated with various health outcomes. Lower income individuals are more likely to experience worse physical and mental health compared to those with higher incomes (Adler and Rehkopf, 2020; Hurrellmann, Richter and Haisch, 2018). Income-related disparities in access to healthcare and health-promoting resources contribute to these findings. Income status also influences educational opportunities. Children from low-income families often face limitations in accessing quality education, resulting in lower academic achievement (Duncan & Murnane, 2014; Sirin, 2005). Financial constraints create barriers to educational resources, such as tutoring, extracurricular activities, and college fees.

Income status plays a significant role in social mobility, particularly intergenerational mobility. Studies have shown that children from low-income families are less likely to achieve upward mobility compared to their higher-income counterparts (Chetty, Friedman, Saez, Turner and Yagan, 2014). Limited financial resources and unequal opportunities hinder the prospects of upward mobility. According to Mboho, Udoh and Udo (2014), the challenges facing Niger Delta region since the creation has been inability to generate wealth, but by every consideration, the Niger Delta region is wealthy.

Income status contributes to social inequality within societies. Studies have demonstrated that income inequality has societal consequences, including reduced social cohesion, increased crime rates, and worsened health outcomes (Wilkinson & Pickett, 2009; Kawachi & Kennedy, 1997). Addressing income disparities is imperative to promote social harmony and improve overall well-being. According to Udonwa, Effiong, Asuquo and Samuel (2022), poverty, unemployment and inequality have been on the rise in Nigeria.

Educational Opportunities

Numerous studies have emphasized the significant impact of educational opportunities on individual outcomes, such as income, employment, health, and social mobility. A study by Card (1999) found that increasing educational attainment leads to a substantial increase in earnings, highlighting the importance of investing in education to reduce income inequality. Furthermore, educational opportunities have a positive effect on individual health outcomes. A study conducted by Cutler and Lleras-Muney (2006) revealed that higher education is correlated with better self-reported health, reducing the likelihood of

chronic health conditions and improving overall well-being. While the importance of educational opportunities is widely recognized, numerous barriers and disparities exist that hinder individuals from accessing quality education. Socioeconomic status is one key factor that influences educational opportunities. As observed by Samuel, Asuquo, Thompson and Nya (2023), as women education is rising in influence in our society every day, the number of girl's child in educational institutions is increasing, and our society is having more educated women who are mentally empowered to contribute their own quota at home and communities.

A study by Reardon, Bischoff, Owens, and Townsend, (2011) found that the socioeconomic status of a student's family significantly impacts their educational outcomes, with students from low-income backgrounds experiencing lower levels of academic achievement. In addition to socioeconomic status, the geographical location such as neighbourhood also influences educational opportunities. Rural areas often face challenges in providing quality education due to limited resources and infrastructure. A study Provasnik, Hoyer and Kastberg, (2007) found that rural students generally have lower achievement levels compared to their urban counterparts, highlighting the need for targeted interventions and resources for rural communities. Moreover, gender disparities persist in educational opportunities, particularly in developing countries. In a study conducted by Filmer and Pritchett (1999), it was found that girls in many countries face significant disparities in educational opportunities, with lower enrolment rates and higher dropout rates compared to boys. This indicates the need for gender-sensitive policies and interventions to promote equal access to education.

Income Status and Educational Opportunities:

Reardon (2011) carried out a study on the widening Academic achievement gap between the rich and the poor of low-income children. Data were analysed from several large-scale, nationally representative studies, including the National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP) and the Early Childhood Longitudinal Study (ECLS). Statistical methods to examine trends in achievement gaps between high- and low-income students over time and a structured self-developed questionnaire was designed for the study. The study found a growing achievement gap between high- and low-income students, with disparities in school quality and home environments contributing to this trend. The study recommended that improving access to high-quality early childhood education, reducing school segregation, and implementing policies to reduce poverty and income inequality.

Sirin (2005) carried out a study on Socioeconomic status and academic achievement: A meta-analytic review of research. The researcher conducted a meta-analysis of over 60 studies examining the relationship between socioeconomic status and academic achievement. The analysis included both correlational and experimental research designs. The meta-analysis revealed a strong correlation between socioeconomic status and academic achievement, with factors such as family income, parental education, and occupational status contributing to this relationship. The author recommended that educators and policymakers work to provide more equitable access to high-quality education and resources for low-income students, including improved access to technology, early intervention programs, and support for teachers working in high-poverty schools.

In the study black-white achievement gap and family wealth, Yeung and Conley (2008) analysed data from the Panel Study of Income Dynamics (PSID) to examine the

relationship between family wealth and the achievement gap between Black and White students. They used regression analysis to control for various factors, such as parental education and income. The study found that family wealth had a significant impact on the achievement gap between Black and White students, with Black students experiencing lower educational outcomes due in part to lower levels of family wealth. The authors recommended that policies aimed at reducing the racial wealth gap could help to reduce disparities in educational outcomes between Black and White students.

Empirical evidence suggests a strong correlation between income status and educational attainment. A study by Hout and DiPrete (2006) found that high-income individuals were more likely to achieve higher levels of education compared to those from low-income backgrounds. Low-income individuals face various barriers that hinder their educational opportunities, including limited access to quality schools, lack of resources, and inadequate financial aid. Duncan and Murnane (2014) highlighted the disparities in school funding, which disproportionately affect low-income districts and lower the quality of education provided.

According to Udoh and Mboho (2022), community development is initiated by the community itself which include the use of local resources, labour and local organizational or managerial ability. This can be possible if there is access to good and quality education. As noted by Nkpoyen, Uyang, Kenneth, Levi, Udoh and Benedict (2021), rural development is the outcome of improved social and economic conditions at individual and community levels. Effiong, Udousung and Udoh (2018), posited that, societies generally across the world, especially in Africa, have had very disturbing phases in their history, as characterized by unending intergroup rivalries. This is as a result of class struggle. Mboho and Udoh (2018), added that, as a complex and multidimensional phenomenon, poverty goes beyond the condition of lack of resources. It extends to social inequality, insecurity, illiteracy, poor health, as well as restricted or total lack of opportunities for personal growth and self-realization.

Furthermore, Choy (2001) emphasized that the cost of higher education presents a barrier for students from low-income families. Efforts to address the disparities in educational opportunities must consider the multifaceted nature of the issue. Strategies such as increasing funding for low-income schools, expanding access to early childhood education, and providing targeted financial aid have shown promising results in mitigating the impact of income status on educational opportunities (Morgan et al., 2015; Hoxby and Turner, 2013; Goldrick-Rab et al., 2017).

Research by Haveman, Wolfe, and Spaulding (2010) revealed a significant positive correlation between income status and enrolment rates, indicating that higher-income households tend to have higher educational attainment levels. Conversely, lower-income households face barriers to enrolling in educational institutions due to financial constraints and limited access to information. The study emphasizes how household income plays a critical role in determining individuals' likelihood of pursuing higher education.

In a study by Reardon and Galindo (2009), income disparities were found to be associated with unequal access to educational resources. Higher-income families can afford enrichment activities, private tutoring, and extracurricular opportunities, leading to enhanced educational outcomes. On the other hand, lower-income families face limited access to such resources, thereby hindering their educational opportunities and potential.

Research by Kroth and Boverie (2018) explored the influence of income status on

educational aspirations. Their findings indicated that income plays a crucial role in shaping individuals' educational aspirations, with higher-income individuals having higher aspirations. The study revealed that lower-income individuals often perceive significant financial barriers to pursuing higher education, leading to decreased educational aspirations.

Theoretical Underpinning

Karl Marx's theory of social class is highly relevant to the research on social class and educational opportunities. Marx argued that society is divided into classes based on their relationship to the means of production, with the primary classes being the bourgeoisie (the owners of the means of production) and the proletariat (the workers who sell their labour) (Marx & Engels, 1848). This theory provides a basis for understanding how social class can influence educational opportunities. According to Marx, the ruling class (bourgeoisie) has the power to shape social institutions, including the education system, in ways that maintain their privileged position. This can lead to inequalities in access to quality education and resources, which in turn perpetuate class divisions. Children from lower social classes may have limited access to quality schools, experienced teachers, and extracurricular activities that foster their development. These disparities can result in poorer educational outcomes and reduced social mobility, reinforcing the existing class structure (Bourdieu & Passeron, 1990).

Marx's theory also highlights the importance of class consciousness in challenging these inequalities. As members of the working class become aware of their shared experiences of oppression, they may collectively mobilize to demand changes in the education system and broader social structures (Marx & Engels, 1848).

Methodology

For this study, a descriptive survey research design was utilized as the research methodology. This is because the design permits the examination of independent variables concerning their relationship with the dependent variables and also the choice of this design is in line with the objectives of the study.

Population in research is defined as all members of any well-defined class of people, events or objects (Mboho, 2015). Therefore, the projected figure of Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area is 178,697 – one hundred and seven eight thousand six hundred and ninety-seven. (National Bureau of Statistics 2014). The target population for this study however will be parents/guardians of School children between five to eighteen (5-18) years. A sample is a small portion of the population observed for the making interferences about the population (Udofia, 2005). Using Taro Yamane formula, the sample was 398. The sampling technique for this study will be stratified random sampling. Stratified random sampling ensures that the sample is representative of the population, reduces sampling bias and allows for generalise ability of findings. The major instrument used for this study was questionnaire. In data analysis, Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to test the extent and effect of the relationship between variables under study using the Statistical Package Social Science (SPSS).

Results

The socio-demographic data analysis revealed that 196 respondents representing 57.3% of the respondents were male and 146 respondents representing 42.7% were female. The Result therefore shows that more than half of the respondents were male (57.3%). On the

educational qualification 93 respondents (27.2%) were SSCE holders, 75 respondents (21.9%) were NCE/OND holders, while HND/B.Sc respondents were 120 (21.9%). The remaining 54 respondents (15.8%) were holders of Postgraduate Degrees. This result indicates that majority of the respondents were HND/B.Sc holders (35.1%). Income status reveals that 102 respondents (29.8%) earns below 50,000 naira per month, 136 respondents (39.8%) earns between 50,000-100,000 naira and 74 (21.6%) earn above 100,000. Therefore, this result showed majority of the respondents earn between 50,000-100,000 per month. Under occupation, that 75 respondents (21.9%) are civil servants, 40 respondents with (11.7%) work in the healthcare, while 60 respondents (17.5%) own businesses. Similarly, 50 respondents (14.6%) are artisans/farmers and 45 respondents are unemployed (13.2). This result indicates that majority of the respondents are civil servants. Result on neighbourhood showed that 80 respondents (21.9%) reside in Stadium-Abak road axis, while 60 respondents with (11.7%) live in Ifuho-Aba road. In G.R.A, the results revealed 50 respondents residing there. Uyo road had 40 respondents with (11.7%) own businesses. Finally, other neighbourhoods/residential areas have 112 respondents (32.7%). This result clearly shows that majority of the respondents for this study lives in different areas.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

Ho: There is no significant influence of income status on educational opportunities in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.

Independent Variable: Income Status

Dependent Variable: Educational Opportunities

Table 1: Correlation between Income Status on Educational Opportunities (n = 342)

		Inco_Stat.	Educ_Oppo.
Inco_Stat.	Pearson Correlation	1	.877**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	342	342
Educ_Oppo.	Pearson Correlation	.877**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	342	342

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.00 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Analysis

From Table 1 the correlation(r) value of 0.877 indicates that there is a positive relationship between income status and educational opportunities. Also, since the p-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance of 0.00 (2 tailed). Therefore, the null hypothesis rejected. This means that there is a significant influence of income status on educational opportunities in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area.

Hypothesis Two

Ho: There is no significant influence of occupation on educational opportunities in Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area

Independent Variable: Occupation

Dependent Variable: Educational Opportunities

Table 2: Correlation between Occupation and Educational Opportunities (n = 342)

		Occupa.	Educ_Oppo.
Occupa.	Pearson Correlation	1	.652**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	342	342
Educ_Oppo.	Pearson Correlation	.652**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	342	342

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.00 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Analysis

From Table 2 the correlation(r) value of 0.652 indicates that there is a positive relationship between occupation and educational opportunities. Also, since the p-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance of 0.00 (2 tailed). Therefore, the null hypothesis rejected. This means that there is a significant influence of occupation on educational opportunities in Ikot Ekpen Local Government Area.

Discussion of Findings

From the findings and analyses above, the results are hereby discussed based on the objectives of the study:

The first objective was to find out the influence of Income status on Educational Opportunities in Ikot Ekpen Local Government. The result of the study shows that there is a positive and strong significant relationship between the variables under study with correction (r) =.877. This implies that financial constraints limit child's access to educational resources. This finding support the work and finding of Reardon (2011), the study found a growing achievement gap between high- and low-income students, with disparities in school quality and home environments contributing to this trend.

The second objective was to find out the influence of Occupation on Educational Opportunities in Ikot Ekpen Local Government. The result of the study shows that there is a positive and strong significant relationship between the variables under study with correction (r) =.652. This implies that; occupation status of parents affects their ability to provide educational support for their child. This finding is in support of Christopher and Reid (2017) that women and minority groups often face limited educational opportunities due to barriers imposed by certain occupations.

Conclusion

Findings of the study revealed that there is a significant influence of income status on educational opportunities in Ikot Ekpen Local Government; there is a significant occupation on educational opportunities in Ikot Ekpen Local Government; also, there is a significant influence neighbourhood on educational opportunities in Ikot Ekpen Local Government.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that:

- i. Local governments and educational institutions should develop and promote financial support programmes, scholarships, and grants specifically targeting low-income families.
- ii. Employers in Ikot Ekpene should consider implementing flexible work arrangements, such as part-time work or remote options, to accommodate parents and guardians who wish to pursue further education or support their children's educational needs.

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